

Quality Education, a Solution to Poverty Alleviation and a Catalyst for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

Quality education is increasingly needed, as it reduces the burden of development problems and acts as a catalyst for sustainable development. Therefore, this study aimed to comprehensively examine the central premise that the manufacturing industry, as a major driver of national development, requires a workforce equipped with high-quality technical and non-technical skills, capacities, and education. The study used a semi-structured survey of 250 employees in the textile and textile product (TPT) manufacturing industry and 85 respondents from the creative industry. The results showed that quality education directly reduced unemployment and poverty through decent work, subsequently driving economic growth. Meanwhile, cases of structural poverty were reduced through the role of quality institutional policies that were transparent and free from corruption and pretense. When institutional policies were undermined by corruption, conditions deteriorate, intensifying development challenges and further increasing inequality. The implementation of this study served as a valuable reference for public institutional policies, particularly regarding the quality of fair and reformist governance. In addition, the analysis also served as a responsible investment in quality education to improve the quality of sustainable education, which was a necessity.

1. Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for poverty eradication are showing the need for quality education for all, in an equitable and sustainable way. SDG 1 may not be achieved by 2030 without progressing in SDG 4, which promotes equitable as well as sustainable education, and SDG 16, aiming to promote just and peaceful institutions (Sorooshian, 2024; Musaddad et al., 2025; Prasetyo et al., 2026). Furthermore, studies show that SDG 3 (health and well-being), SDG 4 (quality education), and SDG 16 (peace, justice, and institutional quality), receive the lowest as well as least favorable ratings (Sorooshian, 2024). Poverty has become a significant obstacle to achieving the SDGs due to its multidimensional complexity, which worsens social inequalities and hinders overall economic development (Musaddad et al., 2025). Therefore, an integrated method is needed to effectively address poverty, leveraging human capital capacity and competency through improving the quality of education as well as institutions as a catalyst and the primary and most important solution (Prasetyo et al., 2026; Prasetyo and Thomas, 2021). The urgency of this study is to explain the acceleration of education quality improvement programs as the primary and most significant solution to reducing as well as mitigating poverty and inspiring the achievement of other SDGs.

In advancing education, integrated, comprehensive, and sustainable long-term investment in quality education is crucial to generate quality human capital assets, both tangible as well as intangible (Prasetyo et al., 2026; Panduwinata et al., 2025; Uribe, 2025; Elkemali, 2024). Prioritizing human capital assets based on quality education can further reduce and break the cycle of poverty, reducing unemployment. Furthermore, the capacity of quality human capital assets is better able to compete globally through innovation, adaptation, productivity, and

creativity, acting as a catalyst for sustainable development (Prasetyo et al., 2026). A study shows that education level substantially influences the relationships among overconfidence, bandwagon behavior, investment sentiment, and overreaction in investment decisions (Wijaya et al., 2025). This is because the implications of knowledge can have a positive impact directly and indirectly on increasing the capacity for innovation, autonomy, and psychological capital (Tran et al., 2025). However, a previous study has shown that equitable resource distribution to address inequalities in educational attainment has had limited success (Gaur et al., 2025). This implies that the role of education in reducing inequality is only 30% of the total existing inequality (Hu et al., 2025).

Numerous studies have been conducted on poverty, development goals, and education. These studies generally tend to prioritize poverty as the primary cause of failure to achieve the SDGs (Ahmed, 2024; Yasir et al., 2024). A previous study had shown a relationship between poverty and education (Ahmed, 2024; Yasir et al., 2024; Panduwinata et al., 2025). The analysis assumed that there was a relationship between educational inequality, poverty, and economic growth as three interrelated factors (Yasir et al., 2024). However, a study by Ahmed (2024) confirmed that poverty was a major cause of illiteracy, and it negatively impacted education from primary to tertiary levels. Another study established that education was a crucial tool for poverty alleviation (Panduwinata et al. 2025). This analysis is based on the understanding that poverty can negatively impact the quality of education. However, the study is more fundamental because low education is a primary cause of poverty, and quality education is considered a crucial element in reducing poverty as well as social exclusion (Mihai et al., 2015). As a result, it is urgent to have strong, fair, and transparent institutional policies in the education sector to break the cycle of poverty. Poor people have equal rights in education based on intelligence, not on cost.

Based on the description above, the argument is that human resources with quality education are able to reduce and break the cycle of poverty, while catalyzing sustainable development (Prasetyo et al., 2026). Without fair and equitable quality education for all, poverty will persist and become increasingly difficult to reduce or eliminate when not urgently recognized. This study shows the central role of quality education as the most significant solution in reducing poverty and a catalyst for achieving other SDGs. The process implies that the objectives of the SDGs without poverty as the main purpose are necessary and should be supported by the achievement of SDG-4. This prioritizes the importance of equitable quality education for all in sustainable development. The specific objective of this study is to comprehensively examine the central premise that the manufacturing industry requires a workforce with strong competencies supported by high-quality technical and non-technical education as a major driver of national development.

2. Literature Review

Economics is a social science in which humans are fully subject to certain moral and ethical values beyond the rule of law. Therefore, few economic theories have appeared that explicitly discuss these moral ethics as the basis for educated individuals and a catalyst for development, as well as addressing the social problems of poverty and unemployment statistically. A related theoretical basis that can be used is the theory of human capital through education (Gillies, 2017; Auerbach and Green, 2024). In general, this human capital theory prioritizes the importance of investing in humans as a primary asset in sustainable development (Prasetyo et al., 2026). Human capital theory states that investment in education can improve the ability of an individual to increase well-being. Other analyses show that education plays a crucial role in driving economic and social development through the progress of competent human resources (Abrha and Weldeyohans, 2025; Sofiani et al., 2025; Ma et al., 2025).

Empirical and theoretical studies show that human capital can play a central role in the success of both nonprofit and for-profit organizations (Sibagariang et al., 2023). Despite its strong relevance to education, human capital theory requires effective implementation supported by robust mechanisms and high-quality institutional policies. Theoretical models further recommend that improving institutional quality promotes human capital accumulation and reduces income inequality, potentially altering the course of historical development (Joilson and Edinaldo, 2012).

Institutional theory in education and human capital management serves as a popular explanation across multiple multidisciplinary fields, namely economics, sociology, politics, culture, and organizations (Najeeb, 2014; Cai and Mehari, 2015). A recent study shows that institutional quality weakens the positive impact of digitalization on technological innovation, while human capital improves this correlation (Odei and Soukal, 2026). The results of the analysis can be used as a comparison in this study. Institutional quality should promote technological innovation and human capital capacity in the digital age. Meanwhile, poor institutional policies and corruption will continue to hinder technological innovation (Bokhari and Seunghwan, 2024). Institutional quality is believed to have a significant positive impact on reducing income inequality. On the other hand, the combination of corrupt institutions substantially worsens income inequality (Prasetyo et al., 2026; Bokhari and Seunghwan, 2024). This implies that even though the literature on corruption is extensive, the process is often fragmented and inconsistent. The process leads to mixed and inconclusive results that can limit theoretical progress as well as sound scientific practice (Meyer et al., 2025). This implies that institutional quality alone is not an absolute prerequisite for human capital to contribute to structural transformation (Gebrehiwot et al, 2025). Therefore, as a basis for the theoretical analysis in this article, a holistic and multidimensional integration of human capital capacity theory and NIE quality is preferred.

3. Research Method.

The method to achieve the objective was designed using an experimental strategy. The primary data source was micro-fundamental statistics obtained through a semi-structured survey. The process was complemented by observational data and interviews with respondents from the creative industry cluster, as well as the textile and garment industry, along with its derivatives. On the other hand, no distinction was made between formal and informal institutions. Respondents were randomly selected and then analyzed in more depth based on predetermined dimensions as well as measurement variables to ensure representativeness. Moreover, the experimental model used to test the theory was general, using simulation methods. The experimental model was designed to examine the causes of observed anomalies, explaining why the underlying problems of poverty, unemployment, and inequality are difficult to resolve, showing the need for diverse potential interventions. This signified that the experimental model was used to provide a basis for testing proposed policies to address the three major issues.

Experimental study designs used several stages to determine the best new theoretical model. It was necessary to formulate hypotheses grounded in established theoretical framework, empirical studies and co-sensitization, to guide this study stage, before the development of the path analysis model results. The process was to develop a framework for problem-solving through a matrix model method, as shown in [Table 1](#). These variables were SDGs-1 (Poverty), SDGs-4 (Education Quality), SDGs-8 (Employment and Economic Growth), SDGs-9 (Innovation and Investment), SDGs-10 (Inequality or Disparity), and SDGs-16 (Institutional Quality). several related SDG variables were selected based on the urgency of the main problem and the study objectives.

Table-1: Path analysis hypothesis matrix model method for solving poverty problems

Peyebab Dampak	SDGs-1	SDGs-4	SDGs-8	SDGs-9	SDGs-10	SDGs-16	Jumlah
SDGs-1		1	1	1	1	1	5
SDGs-4	0		0	0	0	0	0
SDGs-8	0	1		1	0	1	3
SDGs-9	0	1	0		0	1	2
SDGs-10	0	1	1	1		1	4
SDGs-16	0	1	0	0	0		1
Jumlah	0	5	2	3	1	4	$\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$ 15

Source: Six selected target variables from 17 SDGs achievement targets.

Table 1 showed that SDG-4 was the quality education variable with the highest value. This showed that SDG-4 was the main and first cause to eradicate the problem of poverty (SDG-1). Furthermore, this model was described in a path hypothesis as shown in Figure 1. In the process, all arrows started from SDGs-4 directly or indirectly before finally leading to SDGs-1 as the final target. However, there was an interesting process in which the smallest number of causes appeared in SDG-10 (inequality). The analysis showed that the SDGs-10 value was a rival variable for SDGs-4 before the completion of SDGs-1. Therefore, solving poverty was increasingly difficult to solve when inequality still existed. The results of this hypothesis have been proven in previous studies, explaining that economic freedom alone was insufficient to guarantee poverty alleviation (Giorgio, 2024). The results of other studies confirmed that even though poverty alleviation could be achieved, inequality persisted (Breuning and Majeed, 2020; Giorgio, 2024; Elumah et al., 2024).

Figure-1: Hypothesis model of poverty mitigation and prevention

4. Results and Discussion

The result showed that three fundamental development problems, namely unemployment, poverty, as well as inequality, were generally complex and difficult to address. However, empirical studies showed that inequality was the most complex and difficult to handle. Theoretically and empirically, unemployment was the easiest to address, and reducing it decreased poverty. The analysis proposed that although unemployment might decline due to

increased employment, higher income, and strong economic growth, these improvements do not necessarily resolve existing inequality. Under poor institutional conditions from corruption and poor governance, inequality actually increased, both among individuals and groups (clusters). The results were consistent with a previous study showing that poverty remained a significant obstacle to achieving the SDGs. This was due to the complexity and multidimensionality, worsening existing inequalities as well as hindering SDG achievement and prosperity (Musaddad et al., 2025).

Unemployment was a cause of poverty, which had been empirically proven. A decrease in unemployment was in line with an independent decrease in poverty, due to the resulting job opportunities (Prasetyo and Thomas, 2021; Prasetyo and Chayani, 2022). Increased income only reduced individual welfare and could not decrease inequality in society. The problem of inequality actually worsened when institutional governance was also poor due to corruption. Moreover, when governance was poor and institutional quality was weak, the control made it more difficult to eradicate structural poverty. The process occurred because weak institutions were often connected to low levels of education (Avdeeva and Veselov, 2025). In addition, the strategic model for distributing staple food packages to the poor actually promoted laziness and uncreativity, enabling poverty to be more complex and difficult to alleviate. As a result, poverty widened the gap between individuals and unequal groups.

An interesting result from the present study explained that education levels reduced unemployment and poverty, but not inequality. This outcome supported a previous investigation showing that, although the digitalization of entrepreneurship and industry could create new job opportunities and reduce unemployment, the process might also widen the income gap in both rural as well as urban areas (Prasetyo and Setyadharma, 2021; Prasetyo et al., 2025). The result further showed that inequality remained high and difficult to reduce. In some specific cases, inequality actually widened where institutional governance was poor due to corruption. The results were consistent with previous studies, showing that although education improved the quality of human resources, the contribution of human capital to reducing inequality remained limited relative to the broader inequality problem, both at individual and group levels.

Labor-intensive manufacturing industries tended to require more technical education and training than formal education. As more jobs required technical skills, experience became increasingly dominant. Workers with higher levels of education would increasingly excel in the coming years through individual creativity. However, there was no guarantee that higher levels of education would lead to greater success. The determinant of success was the strength of the intangible assets, not the level of formal education. Differences in formal education levels often only occur at the initial stages of employment. Furthermore, skill level, perseverance, and discipline were part of the intangible assets that provided strength.

Poverty remained difficult to eradicate despite improvement in education, largely because institutional quality was still limited, and governance structures were unable to effectively allocate human capital according to individual skills. As a result, human capital became less dynamic in the institutions and was subsequently unable to reduce inequality, even though it reduced poverty. Specifically, a major understanding of this study was the strength of the causal interaction between institutional quality and human capital capacity. The interaction between the two qualities became stronger, the ability to reduce development problems was greater, and vice versa. When institutional quality was dominated by reformists, fairness, and non-corruption, human capital capacity became more dynamic, enabling individuals to develop adaptively as well as productively. In addition, institutional quality governance provided a sense of justice and adaptive freedom to each individual. Human capital

capacity did not develop optimally in environments where institutions fail to provide opportunities, a sense of justice, and dynamism to each individual. This showed that institutional governance became worse when corruption was widespread.

The results could be explained that institutional resources often reinforce the dominant logic of common sense, leading to reformist alternatives. However, the complex and multidimensional cycle of poverty remained difficult to resolve solely through quality education without the role of equitable, reformist institutional quality, further worsening existing inequalities. The results of this study supported previous analysis by Sorooshina (2024), who showed that the role of quality education was partially capable of reducing unemployment and non-structural poverty. The results further strengthened the outcomes of the previous investigation by Gaur et al. (2025). Meanwhile, the quality of reformist institutions was still limited, and the tendency of formal institutions was often not reformist. An example of institutional quality that was generally reformist was social entrepreneurship institutions through the basic concept of socioeconomic solidarity (SWE) in society, generally obtaining the form of informal institutions (Prasetyo et al., 2023). Existing informal institutions were able to mitigate, but not fully resolve, prevailing development challenges. This phenomenon provided further understanding about future study paths, including institutional integrity without corruption.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the major challenges of sustainable development, namely unemployment, poverty, as well as inequality, were deeply interconnected and difficult to resolve. Quality education could only reduce unemployment as well as absolute and relative poverty. Unexpectedly, structural poverty was the most difficult to eradicate independently and had led to increased inequality. This showed that expensive poverty alleviation policies had not been able to reduce poverty personally. Meanwhile, income and wealth inequality had become the biggest obstacles to various poverty alleviation programs, unemployment reduction programs, as well as increased investment and economic growth. In part, the quality of institutions was unable to reduce inequality, as poor institutional governance and corruption had worsened existing inequalities. As the integration of human capital capacity and good institutional quality could reduce unemployment and poverty, the features only partially reduce existing inequalities through the informal institutional dimension of socio-economic solidarity.

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